

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aldehydes by *t*-butyl hypochlorite in aqueous acetic acid medium

B. Thimme Gowda^{*a} and B. S. Moodithaya^b

^aDepartment of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University,
Mangalagangothri-574 199, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Canara College, Mangalore-575 003, India

Manuscript received 6 May 1996, revised 6 September 1999, accepted 26 November 1999

Kinetics of oxidation of formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, propionaldehyde and butyraldehyde by *t*-butyl hypochlorite have been investigated in aqueous acetic acid at 308 K. The reactions show first order kinetics in [*t*-BuOCl], fractional order in [aldehyde] and zero order in [H⁺]. Variation in ionic strength of the medium and addition of reduced products, *t*-butyl alcohol (0–0.05 mol dm⁻³) have negligible effects on the rate, while lowering of dielectric constant of the medium by the addition of AcOH (20–60%, v/v) decreases the rate. Competitive mechanism involving substrate independent and dependent pathways has been suggested. The constancy of the rate coefficient for the substrate independent paths provides evidence for the proposed mechanism.

Carbonyl compounds are unsaturated as well as polar¹. Hence the mechanism of oxidation of aldehydes is important as it could give an insight into a large number of properties of natural products. *t*-Butyl hypochlorite (hypochlorous acid 1,1-dimethylethyl ester) is more stable than inorganic hypochlorites. It is used as an oxidising as well as chlorinating agent^{2–5}. *t*-BuOCl undergoes a two-electron change in its reactions to yield *t*-BuOH and Cl⁻ ion. It liberates iodine from the acidified aqueous potassium iodide⁶. In hydroxylic solvents, it serves as a source of positive chlorine³. We have recently reported the kinetics of oxidation of some carbohydrates in aqueous-alkaline medium⁵. We report herein the kinetics of oxida-

tion of four aliphatic aldehydes by *t*-butyl hypochlorite in aqueous acetic acid.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [oxidant] and [aldehyde]: At constant [aldehyde]₀ (5–50 fold excess over [*t*-BuOCl]₀) and [HClO₄]₀, the first order plots of log [*t*-BuOCl] vs time were linear up to at least 75% completion of the reactions. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots were unaffected by the change in [*t*-BuOCl]₀ (Table 1) establishing first order kinetics in [*t*-BuOCl]. At constant [*t*-BuOCl]₀ and [HClO₄], the rates increased with increase in [substrate] with fractional order dependence.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) for the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by *t*-BuOCl in aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid at 308 K

10 ³ [<i>t</i> -BuOCl] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [aldehyde] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [HClO ₄] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
			H-CHO	Me-CHO	Et-CHO	Pr-CHO
0.3	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.1	–	–
0.5	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.1	8.1	8.9
0.8	2.0	5.0	2.4	–	6.9	8.0
1.0	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.1	6.9	7.4
2.0	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.0	6.9	7.4
3.0	2.0	5.0	2.3	2.0	6.9	7.3
1.0	0.5	5.0	1.2	1.2	2.4	2.6
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.8	1.6	4.0	4.2
1.0	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.1	6.9	7.4
1.0	3.0	5.0	3.4	2.7	10.5	10.8
1.0	4.0	5.0	–	3.6	–	13.9
1.0	5.0	5.0	4.8	4.6	15.7	16.5
1.0	2.0	0.2	2.4	2.0	6.2	5.4
1.0	2.0	2.0	2.4	2.1	6.2	5.8
1.0	2.0	5.0	2.4	2.1	6.9	7.4
1.0	2.0	10.0	–	2.2	7.1	–
1.0	2.0	20.0	2.5	2.6	–	–

Effect of varying other parameters of the medium : Variation in $[\text{HClO}_4]$ (in the range 0.002–0.20 mol dm⁻³), ionic strength of the medium or addition of the reduced product, *t*-BuOH had negligible effects on the rates of oxidations. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by the addition of acetic acid (20–60%, v/v) decreased the rate (Table 2). *t*-Butyl hypochlorite was quite stable in aqueous acetic acid. Addition of small amount of chloride increased its oxidising ability but further additions had little or no effect on the rates. Added acetate ions had no effect on the rate.

Table 2. Effect of varying solvent composition and added chloride on the rates of oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by *t*-BuOCl in aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid at 308 K*

Acetic acid %	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$				
	H-CHO	Me-CHO	Et-CHO	Pr-CHO	
20	2.9	2.8	9.6	9.4	
30	2.8	2.6	9.2	8.7	
40	2.6	2.3	7.9	7.7	
50	2.4	2.1	6.9	7.4	
60	2.0	2.0	–	–	
$10^3 [\text{Cl}^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	0	0.16	0.38	1.1	1.2
1.0	2.4	2.1	4.8	5.6	
2.0	2.4	2.1	–	7.2	
10.0	2.4	2.1	5.7	7.4	
100.0	2.4	2.1	6.9	7.4	
$10^2 [\text{NaOAc}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	0	2.4	2.1	–	–
5.0	2.4	2.1	–	–	
10.0	2.4	2.1	–	–	

* $10^3 [t\text{-BuOCl}]_0 = 50[\text{aldehyde}]_0 = 20[\text{HClO}_4] = 3.33, I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 3. Coefficients of the rate-limiting steps, k_1 and k_2 (dm⁻³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) at different temperatures and the corresponding activation parameters for the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by *t*-BuOCl in aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid

Temp. K	H-CHO		Me-CHO		Et-CHO		Pr-CHO	
	$10^6 k_1$	$10^2 k_2$						
298	–	–	–	–	0.90	1.3	0.90	1.4
303	1.4	0.40	1.5	0.49	1.4	1.7	1.5	2.0
308	2.4	0.59	2.5	0.70	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.8
313	3.8	0.86	4.1	0.99	3.8	3.4	4.0	3.8
318	6.1	1.26	6.5	1.4	–	–	–	–
Activation parameters :								
	k_1	k_2	k_1	k_2	k_1	k_2	k_1	k_2
log A	8.2	8.3	7.9	8.0	7.8	7.9	8.2	7.2
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	81.6	61.6	79.4	60.1	79.4	55.8	81.2	51.4
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	78.4	58.9	76.1	57.7	76.9	51.5	78.8	49.0
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	–98.3	–96.6	–105.4	–99.2	–103.1	–117.0	–96.6	–115.8
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	108.6	88.6	107.6	88.2	108.6	87.6	108.6	84.7

The $[\text{substrate}]_0$ were varied at different temperatures and the coefficients of the rate-limiting steps for the oxidation of all aldehydes have been computed at each temperature (Table 3). The latter constants were employed to calculate the activation parameters (Table 3). The kinetics of first order in [oxidant], fractional order in [aldehyde] and almost zero order in $[\text{H}^+]$ may be explained by a two-pathway mechanism (Scheme 1).

Path 1 :

Path 2 :

where S is substrate (aldehyde).

Scheme 1

The rate law in accordance with Scheme 1 is given by

$$-\frac{d[t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = k_1 [t\text{-BuOCl}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_2 [t\text{-BuOCl}] [\text{S}] \quad (1)$$

Equation (2) may be rearranged as

$$-\frac{1}{[t\text{-BuOCl}]} \frac{d[t\text{-BuOCl}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + k_2 [\text{S}] \quad (2)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k'_1 + k_2 [\text{S}], \text{ where } k'_1 = k_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad (3)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{S}]$ were linear with finite intercepts in conformity with the rate law (3) (vide Experimental). The constants k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the intercepts and slopes of the plots, respectively, by inserting $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = 27.78 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Further, k_1 and k_2 were computed at different temperatures by measuring the rates under varying [aldehyde] at each temperature, for all the four aldehydes. These constants were used to compute the activation parameters for both the pathways (Table 3). The plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger were linear with isokinetic temperatures of 310 and 307 K for the substrate-independent and substrate-dependent paths, respectively. The free energies of activation were almost the same in the respective pathways, indicating the operation of identical mechanisms in all the cases. Further, the constancy of k_1 values for all the compounds indicates that the path-1 is independent of nature of the substrate.

The observed decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium is in conformity with the mechanism involving dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interactions⁷ in the rate-determining steps.

Experimental

t-BuOCl was prepared⁸ in good purity by chlorinating aqueous solution of *t*-BuOH (29.6 g) in the presence of sodium hydroxide (15 g) and sodium carbonate (3 g). The resulting *t*-BuOCl layer was separated, washed with sodium carbonate solution and water. The compound was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride⁹, b.p. 350–351 K. Purity of the compound was checked further by the iodometric method.

The stock solution (0.01 mol dm⁻³) of *t*-BuOCl in pure acetic acid was used. An aqueous solution of formaldehyde (Glaxo) was diluted and standardised by hypiodite method¹⁰. Aqueous solutions of acetaldehyde, propionaldehyde and butyraldehyde (E. Merck) were prepared as and when required. Preliminary investigation showed that the oxidations were extremely slow without the added chloride. Addition of small amounts of chloride (0.001 mol dm⁻³) increased the rate to a measurable level. However, the rate did not increase with further increase in the chloride ion concentration (0.001–0.10 mol dm⁻³). Ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.30 mol dm⁻³ employing concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] >> [oxidant]. The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.0003 to 0.003 mol dm⁻³), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing known amounts of the substrate (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.002 to 0.2 mol dm⁻³), sodium chloride (0.10 mol dm⁻³), sodium perchlorate, water and acetic acid, thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored up to 75% completion by the iodometric estimation of unreacted *t*-BuOCl at regular intervals of time. The rate constants (k_{obs}) computed by the graphical methods were reproducible within ±4% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometries of *t*-BuOCl-aldehyde reactions were determined by equilibrating varying ratios of [substrate] and [oxidant] in aqueous acetic acid at room temperature. Estimation of unreacted *t*-BuOCl in the reaction mixtures showed that one mole of aldehyde reacts with one mole of oxidant. The observed 1 : 1 stoichiometry is represented by equation (4),

where R = H, CH₃, CH₃CH₂, CH₃CH₂CH₂.

The reduced products *t*-BuOCl and Cl⁻ were detected by TLC and silver nitrate test, respectively.

References

- 1 R Brettle in "Comprehensive Organic Chemistry", eds S D Barton and W D Ollis, Pergamon, Oxford, 1979, Vol 1, p 943, and references therein
- 2 A A Zavitsas, *J Org Chem*, 1964, 29, 3086
- 3 C Walling and R T Clark, *J Org Chem*, 1974, 39, 1962
- 4 J N Milovanoic, M Vasojevic and S Gojkovic, *J Chem Soc., Perkin Trans 2*, 1988, 533, 1991, 1231
- 5 B S Moodithaya and B T Gowda, *Z Phys Chem*, 1995, 192, 207
- 6 M J Mintz and C Walling, *Org Synth*, 1973, 5, 184
- 7 E S Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966
- 8 C S Nevin, *Chem Abstr*, 1964, 61, 14530
- 9 H M Teeter and E W Bell, *Org Synth*, 1963, 4, 125
- 10 P Alexander and G Gough, *Biochem J*, 1951, 48, 504